

A New Method for the Determination of Surface Tension of Solids. Part—I.

M. K. Anand, S. K. Solanki, K. C. Jain and V. R. Shastry

Applicability of Parachor equation of Sugden for obtaining the surface tensions of solids has been considered. Surface tensions of solid sodium chloride and some other substances have been calculated, with the help of the equation suggested and the values so calculated have been compared with those, given by various other workers. The variation of surface tension of solids with temperature has been explained in terms of density and surface energy variations. The advantages and limitations of the method have been critically discussed.

Although a great deal¹ of work has been done to obtain surface energies and surface tensions of solids, both from theoretical and experimental view points, a careful survey of the literature reveals that parachor has hitherto not been applied to determine surface tensions of solids. We have, therefore, made attempts in this direction as given below :—

Parachor equation of Sugden² can be put up as,

$$P = \frac{M r_l^{1/4}}{dl - dv} \quad \dots (1)$$

where dl is the density of the substances in the liquid state at the temperature t ; dv is the density of the vapour in equilibrium with the liquid at the temperature t ; r_l is the surface tension of the substance at the same temperature; P and M are the parachor and molecular weight of the substance. Since $dv \ll dl$, dv in the denominator of (1) is usually neglected in comparison with dl and equation (1) takes up the form,

$$P = \frac{M r_s^{1/4}}{dl} \quad \dots (2)$$

It is well known that parachor is more or less independent of temperature, provided, factors like hydrogen-bonding etc., which create complications are absent in the given molecule. It may, therefore, reasonably be assumed that parachor of the given substance possesses nearly the same value in its liquid as well as in the solid state, and that parachor equation (2) obtained initially for liquid state can be extended to solid state also. Hence in analogy with the equation (1) it is possible to write the following equation,

$$P = \frac{M r_s^{1/4}}{ds - dv} \quad \dots (3)$$

where r_s is the surface tension of the solid at the given temperature t ; ds , density of solid at temperature t ; dv is density of vapour in contact with the solid at the same temperature.

1. A. W. Adamson, *Physical Chemistry of Surfaces*, p. 235-261, Interscience Publishers, (1960).
2. S. Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1177.

Since $dv \ll ds$, dv can be neglected in comparison with ds and equation (3) can be written as,

$$P = \frac{Mr_s^{1/4}}{ds} \quad \dots (4)$$

or

$$r_s = \left(\frac{P \cdot ds}{M} \right)^4 \quad \dots (5)$$

Method of Application : It is clear from equation (5) that if P , ds and M are known for a given substance, r_s can be calculated very easily.

Parachor values can be calculated from Sugden's parachor constants³, if its molecular structure is known, or, parachor of the substance can be experimentally determined as usual using equation (2) by finding the densities and surface tensions in its liquid state. One may also utilise standard tables⁴ from which M , r_l and d_s values at the given temperature corresponding to liquid state may be taken up for a given substance and its parachor may be calculated with the help of equation (2). If the substance cannot conveniently be obtained in the molten state at moderately high temperatures, its parachor may be determined, by taking it in a suitable solvent at ordinary temperatures, by using mixture method of Hammic and Andrew⁵.

Densities and molecular weights of solids, may be determined as usual or they can be taken from the standard tables⁴.

Thus knowing parachor of the substance, its density in the solid state and its molecular weight, it is possible to find out surface tension of the solid at the given temperature, using equation (5).

The application of the method to inorganic substances can be illustrated by taking the example of sodium chloride. Sugden's value⁶ for parachor of solid NaCl is 124.8, values for molecular weight and density as given in the Handbook of Chemistry and Physics⁴ for the solid state of NaCl are respectively 58.44 and 2.165 gms/ml at 25°. Substituting these values in the equation (5) surface tension of solid NaCl at 25° is 457.3 dynes/cm. This value is in agreement with values found in references 8, 10 and 11, of the table 1. It is interesting to note that the values for surface tension of solid NaCl given by different workers do not agree and there is an appreciable degree of variance. Survey of the literature reveals that the same is the condition with other solids also. Table 1 also gives an idea regarding the general order of magnitudes of surface tensions (surface energies) of the substances in solid state.

3. S. Sugden, Parachor and Valency, 276, Routledge London, (1930).

4. R. C. Weast, S. M. Selby and Hodgman, Handbook of Chemistry and Physics, The Chemical Rubber Co., 45th Edition, (1964-65).

5. D. L. Hammic and L. W. Andrew, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754.

6. S. Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1295.

TABLE 1

The values of surface tension of solid sodium chloride obtained by various workers

Sl. No.	Worker	Value of surface tension of sodium chloride in the solid state r_s , dynes/cm. or (ergs/cm ²)
1	G.N. Antonoff ⁷	3500
2	Nicolson ⁸	562
3	G.C. Benson and Coworkers ⁹	33-129
4	Zeggeren and G.C. Benson ¹⁰	188, 445
5	S.G. Lipsette ¹¹	400
6	G.C. Benson, H.P. Schreiber and Zeggeren ¹²	276
7	Value by our method	457.3

The application of the method to organic solid substance can be illustrated by taking the example of acetaldoxime. Molecular structure of acetaldoxime is

Sugden's parachor constants³ required for acetaldoxime structure are; C, 4·8; H, 17·10; O, 20·0; N, 12·5; (=), 23·2.

On the basis of this information the value of parachor for acetaldoxime obtained is, 150·8.

From literature⁴, molecular weight of acetaldoxime is 59·07 and its density at 20° is 0·9656 gm/ml. By putting these values of P , M and ds in the equation (5), surface tension of solid acetaldoxime at 20° is obtained as follows,

$$r_s = \left(\frac{P \times ds}{M} \right)^4 = \left(\frac{150 \cdot 8 \times 0 \cdot 9656}{58 \cdot 07} \right)^4 = 36 \cdot 92 \text{ dynes/cm.}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Values of surface tensions of some inorganic substances in solid state, calculated by our method are given in column no. 6th of table 2. These values may be compared with those obtained by Zeggeren¹⁰ and Nicolson⁸, given in columns 7th and 8th of table 2. The fair agreement between the order of the magnitude of the values is striking. Work has also been done on more than 200 nonmetals, metals, organic and inorganic compounds, the results on which will appear in subsequent papers.

7. G. N. Antonoff, *Z. Physikal Chem.*, 1922, **102**, 388.
8. M. M. Nicolson, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1955, **A22**, 490.
9. G. C. Benson and Coworkers, *Canad. J. Phys.*, 1956, **34**, 265.
10. Zeggeren and G. C. Benson, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, **26**, 1077.
11. S. G. Lipsette, Johnson and Mass, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 925, 1940.
12. G. C. Benson, H. P. Schreiber and Zeggeren, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1956, **34**, 1533.

TABLE 2

Surface tensions of some inorganic solids

No.	Sub-stance	Molecular Weight ⁴	Density ⁴ (20°)	Parachor ⁶	Our value. Surface Tension r_s dynes cms^{-1} or ergs cms^{-2} at 20°.	Zeggeren's values ¹⁰	Nicholson's values ⁸
1.	LiCl	42.39	2.068	98.4	531.6	558	—
2.	NaBr	102.90	3.203	148.8	401.5	396	454
3.	NaI	149.89	3.667	170.8	305.1	338	303
4.	KCl	74.56	1.984	156.6	301.4	352	310
5.	KBr	119.01	2.750	174.3	261.8	317	250
6.	RbCl	120.92	2.800	182.8	321.8	323	248
7.	CsF	151.90	4.115	136.9	189.1	190	—

It may be pointed out that theoretical basis of parachor has been shown¹³⁻¹⁴ and since parachor is, more or less independent of temperature, there is ample justification in extending the constancy of the parachor to solid state, in order to determine surface tensions or in other words surface free energies of solids as mentioned already. It may be stated on the basis of literature survey that surfaces in general possess higher values of surface tension in solid state compared to those in their liquid state. Our data given in tables 1 and 2 are in accordance with this finding. It is clear from equation (5) also in which ds appears in numerator, and since ds is generally larger than dl , P and M being constants, it is natural that r_s should be larger than r_l .

The difference between the two surface tension values for two states may be explained in terms of residual forces of attraction between the ions, atoms or molecules in the surface plane. In the case of the solid phase of the given substance, molecules, atoms or ions, are brought much nearer in the surface plane, compared to their distances, when the substance is in the liquid phase. The work done in bringing the molecules etc., at the surface nearer might be getting stored in the surface, in the form of free surface energy or in other words the surface tension.

Another important observation which indicates the advantage of the present method is that equation (5) is capable of giving surface tensions of solids at different temperatures. It predicts that at lower temperature, higher surface tensions should be obtained. Since lower the temperatures, higher are the densities and since ds is in the numerator of the right hand side of the equation (5); the lower the temperature, the higher should be the value of the surface tension of the solid. Physical interpretation for the increasing values of surface tension of solids with decreasing temperature may also be given on the basis of the above discussion. As molecules etc., of the substance in the surface plane come closer and closer

13. Fowler, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1937, **159A**, 227.14. W. V. Bhagwat and V. R. Shastry, *J. V.k. Univ.*, 1963, **3**, 79.

with decreasing temperatures; work done in bringing them nearer and nearer might be getting stored more and more in the surface in the form of higher and higher surface free energy or surface tension.

It may be pointed out in conclusion that at present parachor method can be used to get only an idea regarding the order of magnitude of the values of surface tension of the substance in its solid state. It is not possible to obtain the value for various faces of crystals, various grain sizes etc., of the substances. Since information regarding surface tension values of solids are of theoretical and industrial importance in the case of heterogeneous catalysis, adsorption, etc., further work is in progress.

Thanks are due to Dr. W. V. Bhagwat for his interest in the work.

School of Studies in Chemistry,
Vikram University.
Ujjain.

Received April 20, 1970